

A Black Box Is Absorbing the Wisdom of Human Race

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Recent state-of-the-art Generative Pre-Trained Transformer models has attracted tremendous attention from the public all over the world. While most people focusing on the potentials of these powerful artificial intelligence models in changing our daily lives, I care about the most is that I see the fact that a black box is absorbing the wisdom of human race. Facing the fact I see, I consider there are at least two major issues that need to be addressed sooner or later: 1) looking for new growth points of human wisdom, and 2) preventing the black box from falling into the wrong hands.

1. Introduction

In this brief article, I present a perspective that a black box is absorbing the wisdom of human race, facing the invention of recent state-of-the-art Generative Pre-Trained Transformer (GPT) models from OpenAI (<https://openai.com/>) for artificial intelligence. Primarily, I analyze the technical key points of GPT models. Subsequently, I discuss the essence of GPT models and introduce my perspective. Finally, I give some of my considerations.

2. Technical key points of GPT models

Since OpenAI does not provide the technical details for ChatGPT (<https://openai.com/blog/chatgpt>) or GPT4 (<https://openai.com/research/gpt-4>) besides a recent technical report for GPT4 (OpenAI, 2023), I do not directly analyze the technical details of these two recent state-of-the-art GPT models. However, since OpenAI has stated that ChatGPT is a sibling model to InstructGPT (Ouyang et al., 2022) in introduction to ChatGPT, I suggest that technically referring to InstructGPT can as well reflect the key points of these state-of-the-art GPT models. Fundamentally, GPT models have four technical key points: 1) deep learning, 2) production of a predictive model, 3) production of a reward model, and 4) optimization of the predictive model referring to the reward model.

2.1 Deep learning

The most basic foundation of GPT models is a Transformer-style model (Vaswani et al., 2017), which belongs to the realm of deep learning (mostly, deep neural networks) (LeCun et al., 2015). Basically, deep learning inherits the fundamental goal of machine learning, which is to evolve a predictive model that can map an given input into an expected target (Yang et al., 2022). Therefore, the fundamental function of GPT models is to output an expected target according to an given input, and both the given input and the expected target can be multimodality (Jewitt et al., 2016).

2.2 Step 1: Production of a predictive model

This step contains two contents: 1) collecting a large amount of demonstration data, in

which, with a given input, a labeler demonstrates the expected output to it; 2) training a predictive model, in which, based on deep learning, to produce a predictive model using the collected demonstration data.

2.3 Step 2: Production of a reward model

This step contains two contents: 1) collecting a large amount of comparison data, in which, with a given input and several sampled predictive model outputs, a labeler ranks the outputs from best to worst; 2) training a reward model, in which, based on deep learning, to produce a reward model using the collected comparison data.

2.4 Step 3: Optimization of the predictive model referring to the reward model

Referring to the reward model, the goal of this step is to optimize the previous predictive model via reinforcement learning (Christiano et al., 2017), which results in a better predictive model.

2.5 Summary

Supervised learning based on deep neural networks (supervised deep learning) still is the key technology contributing to the success of GPT models. Therefore, GPT models do not have self-consciousness.

3. Essence of GPT models

Based on the technical key points described in Section 2, the evolving paradigm of GPT models can be summarized as Fig. 1, which reflects the essence of GPT models. In the following contents of this section, I will explain why the essence of GPT models is the production of cramming a collection of human wisdom into a black box and present my perspective.

Fig. 1. Evolving paradigm of GPT models.

3.1 Collection of human wisdom

The demonstration data and comparison data collected in the step 1 and step 2 of the evolving paradigm of GPT models intrinsically represent a collection of human wisdom, since they are produced by humans with their intelligence. Based on deep learning, the step1 and

step 2 transform the collected data, i.e., the collection of human wisdom, into a reward model. Although the resulted reward model is different from the original form of the collection of human wisdom, what cannot be changed is the fact that the reward model is simply another form of the collection of human wisdom. Thus, the essence of the reward model produced by the step 1 and step 2 of the evolving paradigm of GPT models still maintains a collection of human wisdom.

3.2 Cramming a collection of human wisdom into a black box

In the step 3 of the evolving paradigm of GPT models, referring to the reward model, i.e., a collection of human wisdom, the predictive model produced by the step 1 is further optimized via reinforcement learning. In fact, the reinforcement learning with reference to the reward model in the step 3 is a method that can better cram the collected human wisdom into the predictive model produced by the step 1. In recent years, we have also been trying to build better theories and methods for cramming the relatively strong or weak supervisions of some experts into small deep neural networks (Yang, 2020; Yang et al., 2021; Yang, Yang, Chen, et al., 2020; Yang, Yang, Yuan, et al., 2020) for specific applications. I consider the reinforcement learning with reference to a reward model and our recent explorations theoretically share the same purpose which is to better cram a collection of human wisdom into deep neural networks, except that one is based on supervised learning and another is based on supervised or weakly supervised learning (Zhou, 2018). As there still lack of transparent theories for deep learning (Castelvecchi, 2016; Shwartz-Ziv & Tishby, 2017), the predictive model produced by the step 3 is equivalent to a black box, which can give back an output to an input. Thus, in summary, the essence of the step 3 of the evolving paradigm of GPT models is cramming a collection of human wisdom into a black box.

3.3 Perspective

If the step 1 to step 3 of the evolving paradigm of GPT models are iteratively running, what I see is a black box continuously absorbing the wisdom of human race, just like what is shown as Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. A black box is absorbing the wisdom of human race.

From Fig. 2, we can note that, with time goes, the volume of the new collection from the wisdom of human race will firstly increase and then decrease, while the volume of the black box will continuously grow until there is only limited new collection from the wisdom of human race to be absorbed. As a result, the wisdom of human race is existing in another form (a black box which can give back an output to an input, and the input and output of the black box can be multimodality) at a certain speed.

4. Considerations

With the perspective that a black box is absorbing the wisdom of human race, I have two major considerations. I consider that, in a short or probably longer period, human instructors who can continue to feed the black box with wisdom are still needed; however, a big issue is: what should human race do when the wisdom of human race is close to be completely absorbed by the black box? I am kind of worried about this situation, even though I currently am one of those who devote themselves to cramming human wisdom into the black box. Looking for new growth points of human wisdom probably is the solution, otherwise, at least not so many people are needed for their wisdom, because the black box has already replaced them or does not need them anymore. I also consider to whom the black box that has absorbed much of the human wisdom should belong? It must be prevented from falling into the wrong hands.

Author's Note: This article contains only the author's own opinions.

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